

MODEL AND CONTROLLER DESIGN FOR HIGH-SPEED ATOMIC FORCE MICROSCOPE IMAGING AND AUTOTUNING

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INTRODUCTION

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) has been widely used in nanotechnology researches for sample surface characterization since its invention [1]. In its basic form, AFM generates 3D topography images by controlling the probe deflection or oscillation. AFM can characterize sample surfaces with a wide range of properties, conduct imaging in different environments, and be combined with various measurement techniques.

Although AFM has a history over thirty years, its operation still depends heavily on operator experience. For novice users, controller tuning is mostly a trial and error process with risks of damaging the probe or the sample. Therefore, it would be beneficial to provide a comprehensive simulation environment for operator training and controller investigation. In recent years, significant research efforts have been placed on increasing the imaging throughput of the AFM system. The in-plane scanning bandwidth has been increased to over tens of kilohertz with range over tens of microns with new generation scanner design [2] and control algorithm optimization [3]. By utilizing smaller size cantilever probes with specialized optical setup, the out-of-plane tracking bandwidth of the AFM system can also be increased [4]. The development in high-speed AFMs opens up the possibility of observing reaction dynamics on the sample surface. However, the controller tuning procedure becomes more complicated to enable high-speed operation. In addition, the high scanning rate makes the original manual tuning unsuitable since improper controller parameters can damage the sample or the probe in a short time.

To reduce operation overhead and meet the controller tuning demand for high-speed AFM, automated parameter tuning can be a suitable solution. For offline AFM PID controller gain selection, previous research has demonstrated a semi-automated method for parameter adjustment [5]. If a raster scanning pattern is utilized, an iterative learning controller can be trained by scanning

over the initial line for several times until convergence [6]. However, these methods are utilized offline and cannot adapt to sample property variation during imaging.

In this work, we propose a unified model and controller investigation framework for contact mode high-speed AFM imaging performance improvement. The paper is organized as follows. First, we create a lumped parameter model including the cantilever probe, the scanner, and the sample for simulation. Second, we propose imaging parameter tuning algorithms with a relay-based PID auto-tuner and a deflection error based scanning speed auto-tuner. Third, we investigate three methods to improve the performance of high-speed imaging. Fourth, we present a single neuron PID controller to adapt to variation of sample material properties. Performance improvements of the proposed methods are evaluated in simulation with the model to demonstrate their effectiveness. Finally, the investigated models and control methods are organized into a unified framework with switching conditions provided.

AFM SYSTEM MODEL

A number of AFM models with focus on atomic level interaction for physical understanding have been developed in previous research [sim`contact`molecular`hert, 7]. However, instrument level dynamics (e.g. scanner) and controller interfaces are often not available in these efforts. The model developed in this work aims to capture the essential dynamics in contact mode AFM operation with a simplified lumped parameter model in Matlab Simulink for efficient control algorithm investigation.

Out-of-plane Dynamics

The AFM out-of-plane Z-axis dynamics mainly has three components, namely, the cantilever probe, the scanner and the sample. For the cantilever probe, a second-order mass-spring-damper model is sufficient to capture the first resonance. More complex models for higher frequency resonance can be used for other modes

of operation [8]. For the scanner Z-axis, another mass-spring-damper system is used with dynamics matching a scanner previously designed for a high-speed AFM system in our lab. The frequency responses of both the cantilever probe and the scanner are shown in Fig. 1(b). We notice that the cantilever dynamics is faster than the scanner dynamics such that the control loop bandwidth for probe deflection regulation is limited primarily by the sample or the scanner. In addition, the piezo hysteresis non-linearity in the Z-axis is neglected as it can be compensated electrically with charge control methods [9].

The full dynamics of the AFM probe and sample interaction is complicated with the presence of multiple interactions such as the Lennard Jones potential, capillary forces, Van der Waals forces, etc. The tip geometry of the AFM probe can typically be modeled by Hertzian, Johnson-Kendall-Roberts (JKR) or Derjaguin-Müller-Toporov (DMT) models at different levels of complexity. However, even the simplest model has several parameters that are necessary to know but difficult to measure or control. Since lumped parameter models of the sample have proven effective in capturing the dominant dynamics matching the experiment observation for jumping mode AFM [8], the sample is modeled as another mass-spring-damper system with adjustable height and parameter values.

FIGURE 1. (a) Lumped parameter model of out-of-plane dynamics, (b) Simulated displacement output versus force input frequency response of the scanner (scaled by 10^7) and the probe

An illustration of the overall lumped parameter model is shown in Fig. 1(a). In the figure, m_c , b_c and k_c are the cantilever probe mass, damping and stiffness coefficients. Similarly, the subscripts s and p represent the sample and the piezo scanner with (t) indicating time dependency. $F_{cs}(t)$ is the cantilever-sample interaction force, $F_s(t)$ is the disturbance force from sample

variation, and $F_p(t)$ is the piezo actuator force input. $z_c(t)$ is the cantilever deflection. For contact mode operation with sufficiently large reference deflection, the probe and the sample remain in contact and share an added mass. This modular Matlab Simulink model captures the main dynamics for efficient simulation with easy configuration of its sub-components.

In-plane Scanning Model

For the in-plane scanning model, maps for topography height, sample mass, stiffness, and damping with pixel resolution are generated first. A scanner with Preisach hysteresis model and controller previously developed in [10] is used to generate the in-plane location. Bi-linear interpolation based on the scanner position is utilized to compute the time dependent parameters.

AUTOMATIC PARAMETER TUNING

With the complex probe-sample interaction in the AFM probe deflection regulation loop, a PID controller is conventionally used as a generic approach. In this section, we propose an automatic tuning procedure for controller parameter and scanning speed adjustment for AFM imaging.

Automatic PID Tuning

With the modeling complexity and potential variation across sample properties, model-free tuning methods that do not rely on system identification are more suitable. With this requirement, the widely used Ziegler–Nichols (Z-N) tuning method can be utilized for its good disturbance rejection property. For the controller shown in Eq.(1), the Z-N tuning rule of a classic PID controller is $K_p = 0.6K_u$, $K_i = 1.2K_u/T_u$ and $3K_uT_u/40$.

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + K_d \frac{d}{dt} e(t) \quad (1)$$

where $u(t)$ is the control effort, $e(t)$ is the error, K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains respectively, K_u is the ultimate gain when the system started to have stable oscillation with only the proportional gain in the loop, and T_u is the oscillation period.

To automatically determine K_u and T_u without risking unstable oscillation, a relay is used to replace the PID controller as shown in Fig. 2(a). The relay switches between two values with equal magnitude d , which limits the controller output to avoid large amplitude oscillation. As shown in Fig. 2(b), with the relay, a sinusoidal steady oscillation

$e(t) = A \sin(\omega t + \phi)$ can be observed in the error signal similar to the case when ultimate proportional gain is reached. Based on describing function analyses [11], the ultimate gain K_u and the period T_u can be calculated as in Eq.(2).

$$K_u = \frac{4d}{\pi A}, \quad T_u = \frac{1}{2\pi\omega} \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 2. (a) Relay with magnitude d (b) Relay tuning error signal with amplitude A and period T_u (c) Simulated tracking of step topography.

At this point, measuring the amplitude A and frequency ω of the sine wave in the error function $e(t)$ will solve the tuning problem. By finding the second maximum peak in the auto-correlation function of the error $e(t)$ or the relay control effort $u(t)$, the frequency ω and period T_u can be determined. To extract the amplitude A , the formula of a digital lock-in amplifier can be used with the known ω as shown in Eq.(3).

$$\begin{cases} A_{sin} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T e(\tau) \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ A_{cos} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T e(\tau) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ A = \sqrt{A_{sin}^2 + A_{cos}^2} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where T is the sampling time, A_{sin} and A_{cos} are the averaged sine and cosine components during the lock-in process to compute the amplitude. The integration will be replaced by summation due to discrete sampling. The relay based Z-N rule of automatic PID tuning procedure can be summarize in seven steps. First, engage the AFM probe

and disable scanning. Second, set relay amplitude d below maximum allowed probe deflection. Third, deactivate the PID controller and activate the relay unit. Fourth, record the error data $e(t)$ for multiple periods. Fifth, extract the frequency from $e(t)$ with auto-correlation. Sixth, obtain the amplitude with lock-in amplification principle. Seventh, compute K_u , T_u and derive K_p , K_i , K_d .

The simulated step tracking of the PID controller tuned automatically with this procedure is shown in Fig. 2(c). The controller provides good tracking with slight overshoot. Other formula for parameter estimation from K_u and T_u can be used to reduce overshoot with slower response time. Parameter retuning can also be implemented when the line error exceeds the user specified threshold.

Scanning Speed Tuning

A suitable in-plane scanning speed is important to get a good tracking performance and avoid excitation of scanner resonance. To initialize a suitable scanning speed, the sample RMS roughness defined by $R_q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n z_{topo}^2(i)}$ can be estimated to produce an initial guess based on previous operation records. During imaging, the root mean square (RMS) tracking error of a line defined by $e_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n e^2(i)}$ with n being the pixel resolution in X direction. It can be used to adjust the scan speed to be as fast as possible while maintaining e_{RMS} to be smaller than the user defined error threshold. This method can even be applied inline for sample with large roughness variation [12].

HIGH-SPEED IMAGING IMPROVEMENT

In this section, we discuss three methods to improve topography tracking and image generation, which are especially helpful for high-speed imaging. These methods can be used together with the automatic PID tuning procedure.

Location Based Sampling

In a conventional AFM system, the image pixels are sampled at a constant frequency. For trajectories with varying in-plane X -direction scan speed such as a sine wave, this would cause the sampled points to spread unevenly as shown in the top half of Fig. 3. As sine waves are preferred for high-speed scanning to avoid excitation of the scanner dynamics, equal spacing based sampling is needed. For implementation, an in-plane scanner location tracking module is designed with a lookup table.

FIGURE 3. Sine wave scan in fast scanning X direction and constant speed in Y . Equal X spacing sampling yields more uniformly distributed pixels.

Error-corrected AFM Image Generation

For early-stage AFM systems without probe deflection regulation, the topography is measured directly from probe deflection. With regulation of the probe deflection, the scanner control command is recorded as the topography variation. If the proportional constant between the probe deflection signal and the physical height is obtained from calibration, adding the deflection error signal to the scanner command helps to obtain more accurate topography tracking. As shown in Fig. 4, even the tracking performance of the PID controller is poor, the corrected image scan line still matches well with the simulated true topography. The small error remained from the corrected tracking line originates from the deformation of the sample itself. This method has also proven to be useful in imaging experiments [13].

FIGURE 4. Topography feedforward method demonstrates good image generation even with non-ideal tracking due to poorly tuned controller.

Topography Feedforward

With raster scan, the topography variation between adjacent line scans is usually small in common imaging applications. Using the collected data points from the previous line as a feedforward signal can be helpful to reduce the tracking error. Due to different controller responses when scanning from different directions, the trace and retrace lines should be used separately. With discrete sampling, the bi-linear interpolation method is used again to interpolate the estimated upcom-

ing topography based on the last scanned line. For evaluation, the simulated sample has a sinusoidal topography variation with constant material properties. As shown in Fig. 5, the tracking error decreases significantly after the feedforward controller is turned on starting from the third line scan. The initial transient error peak diminishes after several line scans. Compared to iterative learning controllers [14], this method is significantly easier to implement and does not require system identification procedure.

FIGURE 5. Topography feedforward starting at line 3 reduces the RMS error by an order of magnitude for sample with pattern $Z = (Y \sin(X/500) - X \cos(Y/500))/25$ with X, Y, Z units in nm .

ADAPTIVE LEARNING ALGORITHM

The aforementioned automatic controller tuning algorithms and AFM imaging performance improvement methods can handle most of the imaging cases. In this section, we discuss the limitations in handling specialized samples and propose an adaptive algorithm to solve the problem.

Limitation of PID and Potential Alternatives

Since the PID controller is tuned each time based on a single location of the sample, if the material properties vary significantly during a line scan, the controller performance can become poor or even unstable. As shown in Fig. 6, the tuned controller can track the topography well with identical material property while becomes unstable when the sample stiffness varies in a step pattern by 20%. With unknown sample properties, it would be difficult to anticipate the variation to retune the PID controller so that an adaptive algorithm other than a simple PID controller is needed.

Robust control, adaptive control, and fuzzy logic control techniques are commonly utilized to han-

FIGURE 6. Imaging the sample with identical topography as Fig. 3 but with 20% step variation in the sample stiffness map. Properly tuned PID controller can track high stiffness area well but becomes unstable at low stiffness area.

de modeling parameter uncertainties and changing system properties. As the complex contact mechanics is difficult to model, system identification based controller tuning is needed. As an alternative, data-driven methods such as deep reinforcement learning have demonstrated their capability in handling complex model-free control problems. However, with high bandwidth signal processing running on Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA), the real-time computation of deep neural networks can be challenging.

Single Neuron Adaptive PID

Among various algorithms, the Single Neuron PID (SNPID) controller is a suitable solution to resolve this problem with its good balance between algorithm complexity and adaptive performance. The adaptive algorithm is based on the Hebb learning rule and is computationally inexpensive due to its simple structure [15]. We present the discrete-time implementation of the SNPID controller.

The controller architecture of the single neuron PID is shown in Fig. 7(a). The inputs of the neuron $x_P(n)$, $x_I(n)$ and $x_D(n)$ are given in Eq.(4).

$$\begin{cases} x_P(n) = e(n) - e(n-1) \\ x_I(n) = e(n) \\ x_D(n) = e(n) - 2e(n-1) + e(n-2) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $e(n)$ is the error signal of sample n . The neuron output $u(n)$ is updated at each cycle with the increment Δu as shown in Eq.(5).

$$\begin{cases} \Delta u(n) = \frac{K(w_P(n)x_P(n) + w_I(n)x_I(n) + w_D(n)x_D(n))}{w_P(n) + w_I(n) + w_D(n)} \\ u(n+1) = u(n) + \Delta u(n) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where K is a constant gain, $w_P(n)$, $w_I(n)$, $w_D(n)$ are weights at sample n updated with Eq.(6).

$$\begin{cases} w_P(n+1) = w_P(n) + \eta_P e(n) u(n) x_P(n) \\ w_I(n+1) = w_I(n) + \eta_I e(n) u(n) x_I(n) \\ w_D(n+1) = w_D(n) + \eta_D e(n) u(n) x_D(n) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where η_P , η_I , η_D are positive constant learning rates. It can be proven by stochastic approximation theory that the formula has a form similar to that of the classic gradient descent method. With sufficiently small learning rates, the weights of the neurons converges to a steady state value [15].

FIGURE 7. Single neuron PID controller: (a) architecture for weight update (b) good tracking performance for sinusoidal sample topography with step variation in the sample stiffness map

Similar to the neurons in artificial neural networks, the SNPID controller weights are adjusted with new data. A total of seven constants are initialized by the operator. For convergence, the gain K is set to a small value of 0.1. The learning rates η_P , η_I , η_D are set all to 1 and initial values of $w_P(0)$, $w_I(0)$, $w_D(0)$ all set to 0.1. The simulation results using the SNPID controller is shown in Fig. 7.

Compared to a classic PID controller as shown in Fig. 6, the SNPID controller remains stable regardless of the varying material property. The weight adjustment capability of the SNPID controller allows it to adapt to the parameter variation online. With this capability, AFM imaging of samples with significant property variations can be conducted without operator intervention. One minor drawback of this method is that the learning rate might need some manual tuning to ensure the convergence of the weights.

CONTROLLER AUTOMATION FRAMEWORK

With the proposed controller architecture in Fig. 8, three image level improvement methods can be activated at all time. The system performs automatic PID and line speed parameter initialization and start imaging. To handle samples with large material property and topography variation, the roughness R_q and the relative error

$e_{relative} = e_{RMS}/R_q$ is computed online. If percentage variation within a single line exceeds a predefined threshold, the controller switches into adaptive mode with online parameter updates based on the user initialized learning rates.

FIGURE 8. Framework of the proposed controller

CONCLUSION

In this work, we modeled the AFM imaging dynamics and proposed an automatic tuning method for PID controller with scanning speed adjustment. Location based sampling, topography feed-forward, and error-corrected AFM image generation methods are evaluated for their ability to improve high-speed imaging performance. To handle imaging of samples with varying properties, a single neuron PID controller is proposed with criteria for controller switching. For future work, a graphical interface of the simulation for education purpose is under development. Algorithm implementation on custom AFM systems and extension to other modes of operation are also interesting directions to pursue.

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